

PROCESS OF FORMATION OF THE POND WATERS

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Annotation: The article contains information about the salting process of the collector-drainage networks of the Bukhara region.

Key words: Collector-drainage, saline washing, irrigation

Introduction: Finding new sources of water is one of the most important tasks in Central Asia, where the water shortage is felt strongly. For this reason, expanding the use of local water resources - collector-water, underground and waste water in agriculture creates opportunities to prevent the negative consequences of water shortage. Bukhara region's demand for water has long been met by the Zarafshan river, which is fed by mountainous terrain. Due to the increasing demand for water in the upper part of the river, the share of Zarafshan water reaching the territory of the region has decreased over the years. In the Karmana mountain range, its average annual water consumption was 100-120 cubic meters until the 1980s. meter second, and in the early 1990s it was 70 cubic meters. it was only about a meter second. Nowadays, the water of the river runs out completely within the territory of Navoi region. The part of Zarafshan that passes through the Bukhara region is called the Central Bukhara ditch, drains sewage and collector waters.

The water shortage in the lower part of Zarafshan necessitated the digging of the Amu-Bukhara canal. In 1962, Amu-Karakul, in 1965 the first, and in 1975 the second (232 km long) Amu-Bukhara canal was commissioned. This channel begins near the town of Chorjoi and flows to the Dengizkul plateau. After that, the water from the

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canal is raised up through several stages of suction stations (only "Hamza"-I-II suction stations can raise up to 50 meters). It flows to the reservoirs of Tudakul, Kuyimazar and Shurkul and is distributed through irrigation channels. The water demand of the region's population and farms is currently being met by the full Amudarya water. The amount of this water has now become somewhat stable, and the average annual flow in the main part of the channel is 145-170 cubic meters. meter is a second.

It is known that there are irrigated lands in Bukhara region in three places: Bukhara, Karakul and Qarovulbazar oases. A system of ditches was created in order to improve the land reclamation conditions here. Most of them are open ditches. One and a half cubic meters every year. km. The volume of sewage and waste water is removed from the oasis. A small part of these waters with varying degrees of salinity flows into the Amudarya basin through the Katta-tuzkon lake and the Porsonkul ditch. The rest of the main part is collected in shallow lakes such as Dengizkul, Karakyr, Ogitma. According to rough calculations, 5 mln. t. salt and various harmful chemicals accumulate around it. This has a negative impact on the ecological situation in the region. Currently, the main ditch "Shurdarya" is being built at a rapid pace in order to drain the waste water and ditch water from the oases in the southwestern part of Uzbekistan to the Aral Sea. Part of it passes through Bukhara region. In the future, taking into account the interests of fisheries and nature protection, it is necessary to direct the ditch waters to "Shurdarya" and to accelerate measures to fundamentally improve the ecological environment.

There are 8599.5 km (241.23 thousand ha) long collector networks to maintain a stable amelioration condition of cultivated areas of Bukhara region, and its relative length per hectare is 31.27 p. meters. Of this, open collectors cover 7604.47 km (180.04 thousand ha), 617 vertical drainage wells exist on an area of 42.82 thousand hectares, and 18.37 thousand hectares with the help of closed-bed collectors, while reducing the level of underground seepage water. has been serving to improve land reclamation. In order to study the performance of collector-drainage networks in the irrigated lands of Bukhara region, the total ditch water flow in the years 2010-2019, the flow released from 1 hectare, the ditch flow module and the ratio of the ditch water

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flow to the water consumption for crop irrigation and salt washing were analyzed. When using collector water, it is important to know the permissible amount of salts contained in it. Factors such as the salt content and composition of water, soil properties, and land reclamation conditions should be taken into account.

The period of the highest rise of the groundwater level corresponds to the month of August and the lowest period corresponds to the month of December. The amplitude of the one-year change of waters is 0.04 m. In the conditions of Bukhara region, in order to improve land reclamation or to maintain it at the same level, it is necessary to release at least 40-45 percent of the water supplied to irrigated areas through drains. Otherwise, it will lead to a violation of the water-salt balance in the fields. In 2017, 2669.61 million m³ of leachate was released from irrigated areas in Bukhara region through collectors. Of this, 2626.75 million m³ was released through collectors and 82.18 million m³ through vertical drainage wells.

Summary: In Qarovulbazar and Olot districts of Bukhara region, each liter of water coming out through the collectors contains up to 5,243 grams of different salts, while in Gijduvan district this figure was 2,768 grams. In 2019, 98.7 million m³ of collector water was used for irrigation. Underground seepage waters of the lower regions of Bukhara, Kogon districts, as well as part of water from the collectors of Jondor district are discharged to "Dengizkul" and "Bosh suv tashlama" through the "Parallel" main tract, and are discharged to "Amu Darya" through the "Parsankul" discharge. The water released from the "Parallel" main tract is 603.74 million m³ and its mineral content is 5.99 g/l. During the year, 5.65 million tons of various harmful salts fell into the irrigated areas with the water taken to the border of the region, and 9.07 million tons of harmful salts were released from these areas through the collectors. Compared to the salts that came with water, the released salts were 3.42 million tons more, which showed that the level of salinity in the active layer of the irrigated lands was reduced.

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